

EFFECT OF BIO-ORGANIC FERTILIZER (Boostract®) ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF AMARANTHUS (*Amaranthus* spp) VARIETIES AT GWAGWALADA, ABUJA

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at Teaching and Research Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, main campus along Airport road, with the geographical coordinate of latitude of 8.1°N and longitude of 7.04°10"E during the Dry season to determine the effect of bio-organic fertilizer on the growth and yield of Amaranthus varieties at Gwagwalada, Abuja. The treatment consisted of three levels of Boosttract bio-organic fertilizer (0,5ml and 4ml) and 2 varieties of amaranthus (black seed amaranth and white grain amaranth). The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and replicated three times. Growth parameters such as plant height, number of leaves were higher when the application of 5ml was applied. The results show that the application of 4ml on black seed amaranth results to a larger leaf area while the application of 5ml on white grain amaranth results in the highest yield in Abuja, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Amaranthus caudatus is grown for its leaves and is among the highly prized leaf vegetables in Nigeria, due to their high nutritional and commercial significance. Amaranthus belongs to the genus of flowering plants in the family Amaranthaceae, commonly known as amaranths. They are known for their colourful, long-lasting flowers, and are popular as ornamental plants. Some species are also grown for their edible leaves and seeds, which are rich in protein and minerals. The leaves and seeds of some species were used as a source of food, while others were used for medicinal purposes. Today, Amaranthus is still cultivated in some regions for its leaves, which are used as a leaf vegetable, and its seeds, which are a source of grain. Some species of Amaranthus are grown as ornamental plants for their colourful foliage and attractive flowers. The leaves and seeds of some species of Amaranthus have been used in traditional medicine to treat various ailments, such as

headaches, inflammation, and digestive problems. In some regions, the leaves of Amaranthus are used as feed for livestock.

The seeds of some species of Amaranthus are used as a source of oil, while the plant's fibres are used in the production of paper and textiles. However, nowadays amaranth is an important cereal because it is gluten-free and contains about twice the crude protein of wheat, rice, and maize and is high in fibre (8%), lysine, iron, magnesium, and calcium.

Most vegetable farmers in tropical Africa are smallholders who can't find the money for the value of inorganic fertilizer though soil fertility limits the yield of vegetables especially in urban and periurban facilities (Makinde *et al.*, 2010). Amaranthus requires soils with excessive natural content and ample nutrient reserve for the finest yield subsequently fertilizer appears to be a reliable source of nitrogen in giant extent for developing amaranthus. The use of organic fertilizer has determined favour in boosting

crop production in Nigeria, due to the fact it is cheap and less probably to grant the groundwater and it improves soil fertility states as well as increasing the earnings of farmers by way of extending yield.

Organic fertilizers are natural materials derived from plant or animal origin, there are several positive values for using organic fertilizers, for instance, soil value, crop value, biological value, environmental value, economic value, human health and soil quality (Haruna *et al.*, 2020). Application of organic fertilizer cannot only improve soil fertility, soil physical and chemical properties and enhance soil water storage capacity but also effectively promote the vegetative growth and reproductive growth of plants, thereby improving the quality of plants. Fertilizer application rates in intensive agriculture systems have increased drastically in recent years in Nigeria, farmers depend largely on locally sourced organic fertilizer (Makinde *et al.*, 2010). The effects of organic fertilizer on *Amaranthus* depend on the concentration used and the stage of plant development in general, organic fertilizer increases the height, leaf area and yield of *amaranthus*. However excessive use of organic fertilizer can have negative effects on the plant such as stunted growth, reduced yield and decreased seed germination rate. Research has shown that organic Fertilizers are less leached into groundwater than chemical fertilizers. Organic fertilizers have a positive effect on the root growth of plants by increasing the root rizhosters condition (structure and humidity) and plant growth is encouraged by increasing the population of microorganisms (Fatima *et al.*, 2007).

This study was undertaken to determine the suitable variety for optimum yield in the study area and to determine the level of Boostract that is suitable for optimum growth and higher yield of okra at Gwagwalada.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted during the rainy season of 2023 at the teaching and research farm of the faculty of agriculture, university of Abuja, Nigeria (latitude of 8.1°N and longitude of 7.04°E). Based on climate; the area is characterized by 2 distinct seasons which are the rainy season from April to August and the dry season from October to February. The average monthly temperature over the year ranges from 24°C - 30°C while the average relative humidity ranges from 87.0% to 76.0%, the month of June recorded the highest amount of rainfall.

The experiment was laid in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) consisting of 3 replications and 5 treatments producing 18 experimental plots in total. The treatments were V10 (black seed amaranth with 0 ml/l Boostract), V14 (black seed amaranth with 4 ml/l Boostract),

V15 (black seed amaranth with 5 ml/l Boostract), V20 (white seed amaranth with 0 ml/l Boostract), V24 (white seed amaranth with 4 ml/l Boostract) V25 (white seed amaranth with 5 ml/l Boostract) contains 2-*Amaranthus* varieties (black amaranth and white grain amaranth) and 2-levels organic fertilizer (Boostract®) at 5ml, 4ml per litre of water and 0ml as control. A nursery bag with a diameter of 1.32m was used to represent one plot with a pathway of 1m between each replicate and 0. Each nursery bag was filled with 12kg of fine loam soil from previously ploughed land. 0.50 gram of seed was broadcasted in each nursery bag and irrigation was used to supply water to the plant. 4ml and, 5ml of Boostract was mixed into 1 litre of water and applied according to the treatment combination and the application was repeated twice at an interval of one week making a total of 2 applications. The first dose of fertilizer was applied 3 weeks after sowing while the second dose was applied on the 4th week.

Weeding was done after sowing at 2-week intervals from the previous weeding by hand pulling.

Harvesting was done manually at 6 weeks after sowing. The vegetable was pulled from the soil with the root and was taken to the crop science laboratory for measurement using an electric weighing balance. Data collection was done on each plot, 3 plants in each plot were randomly selected and tagged for measurement every week starting from the 3rd week after sowing, 4th week after sowing, 5th week after sowing and 6th week after sowing and the average was recorded per plot.

Data was collected on the following parameters:

1. Number of leaves per plant

The number of leaves of all the tagged plant was counted at interval of one week and the average recorded starting from the 3rd week up until the 6th week and sowing.

ii. Plant height (cm)

The plant height was measured from the ground level to the tip of the plant for 3 randomly tagged plants per plot in the 18 plots. This was done using a measuring tape at the various sampling periods and the average was calculated and recorded per plot. The data was collected from the 3rd week after sowing up until the 6th week after sowing

iii. Leaf Area

The diameter of the leaf was determined from the 3 plants per plot on the broadest active leaf per plant, and the maximum width of the leaves was determined using a meter rule from the 3 tagged plants starting from the 3rd week up until the 6th week.

Leaf Area (LA) = f(L, W)

iv. Fresh Leave Yield

The plant was harvested on the 6th week and

was weighed on a per per-plot basis. The vegetable (amaranth) yield per plot was determined using a weighing balance. The yield from each 18 plot was weighted in grams and recorded.

Data Analysis

All data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the SAS version 9.4 statistical package, the means were separated using LSD at 5% level of significance.

RESULTS

Plant Height

The result of this study shows no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in plant height among the treatments at 3 and 4 weeks after sowing (table 1). At five weeks after sowing maximum height (24.60 cm) was recorded for black seed amarantus with 5 ml Boostract which was significantly similar to the height recorded for white amarantus with 5 ml Boostract and black seed amarantus with 4 ml Boostract. While black and white seed amarantus with 0 ml Boostract has the shortest plant height. The plant height documented for treatment 5, 3 and 2 (31.90, 30.27 and 30.03 cm) were significantly the same at week 6 after sowing and treatment 1 and 4 also has the shortest height.

Table 1: Effects of Boostract on plant height for amarantus at different weeks after sowing

Treatments	Plant Height at 3WAP	Plant Height at 4WAP	Plant Height at 5WAP	Plant Height at 6WAP
V10 +0ml/L	3.03	12.70	17.60	23.87
V15+5ml/L	3.83	14.70	24.60	30.03
V25++5ml/L	2.90	14.17	22.87	30.27
V20+0ml/L	2.53	14.30	17.77	24.90
V14+4ml/L	3.50	11.77	23.33	31.90
V24+4ml/L	3.33	6.933	20.63	28.70
Significance	ns	ns	**	*
SE±	1.05	3.43	1.09	1.62
LSD @ 5%	3.29	10.81	3.42	5.09

Means were separated using LSD at $p \leq 5\%$ V10= control black seed amarantus

V15= black seed amarantus with 5ml V14= black seed amarantus with 4ml

V20= white seed amarantus V25= white seed amarantus with 5ml

V24= white amarantus with 4ml

Number of Leaves

Table 2 reveals that number of leaves per plant was significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by the treatments at 4th and 5th weeks after sowing. More number of leaves was recorded for black seed amarantus with 5 ml Boostract at 4 weeks after sowing which was significantly the same with the number of leaves noted on the other treatments excepts for black and white seed amarantus with 0 ml Boostract. At three weeks

after sowing, white amarantus with 5 ml Boostract significantly performs better in terms of number of leaves than the other treatments. The number of leaves recorded for treatment 2 at 5WAP was significantly the same number of leaves recorded for treatment 4, 5 and 6, but greater than that recorded for treatment 1.

Table 2: Effects of Boostract on the number of leaves for amarantus at different weeks after sowing

Treatments	Number of leaves at 3WAP	Number of leaves at 4WAP	Number of leaves at 5WAP	Number of leaves at 6WAP
V10 +0ml/L	7.00	9.77	10.80	13.43
V15+5ml/L	6.53	11.70	15.20	15.10
V25++5ml/L	6.43	11.53	20.00	24.57
V20+0ml/L	7.00	10.00	12.10	14.13
V14+4ml/L	6.23	10.83	14.67	15.20
V24+4ml/L	6.47	11.67	14.13	16.67
Significance	ns	*	**	ns
SE±	0.34	0.38	1.30	2.52
LSD @ 5%	1.07	1.21	4.11	7.93

Means were separated using LSD at $p \leq 5\%$ V10= control black seed amarantus

V15= black seed amarantus with 5ml V14= black seed amarantus with 4ml

V20= white seed amarantus V25= white seed amarantus with 5ml

V24= white amarantus with 4ml

The leaves area was not significantly ($p < 5\%$) different among the studied kook at 3, 4, 5 and 6 weeks after sowing (Table

3). At weeks 5 and 6 maximum leave area was observed in treatment 5 and the lowest leave at weeks 3, 5 and 6 was noted in

Table 3: Effects of Boostract on leave area for amarantus at different weeks after sowing

Treatment	Leave Area at 3WAP	Leave Area at 4WAP	Leave Area at 5WAP	Leave Area at 6WAP
V15+5ml/L	3.43	9.13	23.33	22.17
V14+4ml/L	3.50	20.90	36.43	31.87
V20+0ml/L	3.43	23.23	30.03	32.60
V25++5ml/L	2.37	12.67	22.37	21.27
V24+4ml/L	2.83	15.47	43.33	40.20
V10 +0ml/L	3.13	17.77	33.20	33.27
Significance	ns	ns	ns	ns
SE $\pm$	0.54	3.71	5.52	6.18
LSD @ 5%	1.69	11.71	17.39	19.46

Means were separated using LSD at $P \leq 5\%$

Fresh Leaf Yield

The plant height was significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by the two factors (varieties and Boostract levels) tested as obtained in Table 4. Treatment V15 (black amarantus + 5 ml Boostract) has the maximum plant height (18.29cm) and was significantly not taller than the plant height recorded for the plot of white amarantus with 5 ml Boostract (17.55cm) and black amarantus with 4 ml Boostract (17.63cm). The lowest plant height mean was noted in the plot of black amarantus with 0 ml Boostract and was significantly similar with the plant height of other treatments except treatment V15 (black amarantus with 5 ml Boostract). Black amarantus significantly responded well to the application of Boostract at 4ml when compared with the other variety. The number of leaves was significantly ($p < 5\%$) the same among the treatments except for white amarantus with 5 ml Boostract which has the highest number of leaves and performs better than other entries.

The plot of black amarantus with 4 ml boot

rack has a greater leave area mean which does not vary from the left area mean documented for black amarantus with 5 ml, white amarantus with 5 ml and white amarantus with 4 ml. V10 has the smallest leave area (14.52) and was similar to that recorded for V20 (14.67) in this evaluation. This indicates that the application of Boostract at 4 and 5 ml significantly results in a wider leave area irrespective of variety.

Application of 5 ml of Boostract to white seed amarantus has the maximum mean fresh weight (159.73) and was only significantly ($p < 5\%$) greater than the weight recorded for black and white seed amarantus with no fertilizer (controls). White seed amarantus with the application of 5 ml of Boostract has the heaviest total yield mean (154.43). The increment in biofertilizer rate (from 4 ml to 5 ml) does not significantly improve total yield and the controls have the lowest yield.

Table 4: The effect of Boostract application on some growth and yield traits of amaranthus

TREAT	Plant Height	Number of Leaves	Leave Area	Freshweight	Yield
V10	14.30b	10.25b	14.52b	96.30b	92.83b
V15	18.29a	12.13b	23.18a	158.53a	150.70a
V25	17.55ab	15.63a	22.33a	159.73a	154.43a
V20	14.87b	10.81b	14.67b	102.27b	98.57b
V14	17.63ab	11.73b	25.46a	155.08a	150.20a
V24	14.90b	12.23b	21.84a	145.70ab	141.43ab
Significance	*	**	*	*	*
SE±	1.08	0.71	2.51	14.14	13.68
LSD @ 5%	3.07	2.01	7.14	44.55	43.10

Means were separated using LSD at $p \leq 5\%$ V10= control black seed amaranth
V15= black seed amaranth with 5ml V14= black seed amaranth with 4ml
V20= white seed amaranth V25= white seed amaranth with 5ml
V24=white amaranth with 4ml

DISCUSSION

The combined result of this evaluation agrees with the report of other researchers who have shown that crop performance could be affected by the rate of bio-fertilizer applied and crop variety type. The crop performance also varied as the age increased depending on the variety and amount of Boostract applied.

The increase in the plant height and other growth parameters noted in this study confirms the result of Yaseen *et al.* (2021) who observed maximum plant height at maturity, number of leaves per plant, individual leaf area, LAI, primary and secondary branches per plant from application of biofertilizer

(Azotobacter +PSB + KSB), whereas minimum growth was recorded with no biofertilizer. The workers suggested that the increase in those traits might be due to the timely supply of required plant nutrients in the form of biofertilizers which resulted in better nutrition and increased photosynthetic activity, enhanced cell division and enlargement. This result is similar to the study

of Gayathri and Anita 2018, where the use of organic fertilizers such as Azospirillum, VAM fungi and Phosphobacteria has resulted in better growth performance of lady's finger and amaranth. It has been observed that biofertilizers fix an appreciable quantity of atmospheric nitrogen in soil; aid plant growth by production of organic acid and growth hormones and make available the complex phosphorus to the plant, which may lead to a reduction in mineral fertilizer required.

This study revealed that several leaves and areas can be positively enhanced with improvement in plant nutrition by Boostract. The treatment of crops with organomineral fertilizer increased the fresh matter and number of leaves of grain amaranth as shown by Akanni *et al.*, 2011. Mamatha and Bagyaraj, (2003) noted that application of Azotobacter increases the number of leaves in tomato.

It has also been evident from this study that Boostract application improves the yield of amaranthus (white and black seed). This supports the report of Alamene and Howells,

(2022) who carried out an evaluation of sustainable bio-liquid fertilizer (supergro) on the production of fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*) in Nigeria and observed that application of SuperGro significantly influenced its leaf area and total dry matter. Shinde et al., 2018 in their investigation also indicated that the application of biofertilizers influenced the growth, yield and quality of spinach in general.

CONCLUSION

It could be concluded that the application of Bioextract at 5ml per litre to white seed amaranth recorded the best performance in Abuja.

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